

Meeting a scientific facility provider's duty to maximise the value of data

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Science and Technology Facilities
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Big Science

Particle Physics
Earth Observation
Astronomy

ILL and ESRF

CERN: LHC

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

ESA: Top Sat

Small Science

ISIS Neutron Source
Diamond X-ray Source
UK Central Laser Facility

SKA

ESO: E-ELT

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Science & Technology
Facilities Council

Big Data, Big Computers

Facility Data Archives

All **ISIS** data (~25 years) > 3,000,000 files

All **Diamond** Data (~5 years) > 100,000,000 files

CERN LHC Tier 1 Data

UK hub for **LHC** data (~3 years: 11PB)

Computing Architectures:

- 1 - the UK's most powerful computer (IBM BlueGene/Q :1.4 petaflops)
- 2 - the UK's most powerful graphics processor computer (190,000 graphics cores : 248 teraflops)
- 3- large commodity computing server (7000 processor cores)
- 4 - high throughput super-data-cluster (4.6 petabytes of parallel file storage with 1 terabit per second aggregate bandwidth from the data to the processors)

The
StorageTek
tape robot
100PB
Capacity

Maximise the value of STFC data

- 1) Researchers access their own data
- 2) Other researchers validate published results
- 3) Meta-studies incorporating data
- 4) Set experimental parameters and test new computational models
- 5) Used for new science not yet considered
- 6) Defend patents on innovations derived from science
- 7) Evidence based policy making

Data Re-use

Facilities Lifecycle

ICAT
Metadata Repository

Data Preservation Infrastructure

Automated Metadata Collection

- Schedule & Proposal: who, funder, what
 - Except 5% don't do what they proposed
- Instrument: data, instrument settings
- Publication: analysis method, result
- DOI is address for linking

Preserve which data?

Raw & calibrated data:
owned by facility,
preserved by facility

- Derived Data Provenance
- Derived Data Ownership – user, funder
- Analysis software preservation
- DOI for software versions

Cite which data ?

- Facility centric view
 - Investigation is allocated beam time
 - Investigation lasts 5 minutes to 2 weeks
 - Investigation is allocated DOI
 - Investigation is cited
- Metadata levels/model – what level DOI
 - Investigation/experiment
 - Data set(s)
 - Individual file(s)

Core Scientific Metadata Model (CSDM)

- <http://code.google.com/p/icatproject/wiki/CSMD>

When to publish data?

- Commercial data
 - < 1% of data
 - subject to individual contracts
 - Don't publish
- Data Policies – different science, different facilities, different policy
- Data Embargo – PhD period 3 years
- Record who accesses data
- Metadata Embargo – 2004 Haumea example

Avoid data mis-use

- Sensitive data
 - Satellite images of New York 9/11/2001
- Making large data sets usable
 - UN IPCC Report 5 data
 - CERN LHC experiment data
- Publish samples for teaching
- Avoid time wasting by conspiracy theorists
- Science should be verifiable

ROI in data centres ?

- Cost of data curation
 - ESA mission based approach
- Recent reviews of 2 UK data centres by Neil Beagrie and John Houghton
 - Interview based approach
- ENSURE EU project
 - <http://ensure-fp7-plone.fe.up.pt/site/>
 - Cloud based costs
 - Value of data for preservation objective

